

**DEVELOPMENT OF A TURBINE MACHINE DESIGN USING THE PARAMETRIC METHOD
TAKING INTO ACCOUNT MULTI-PHYSICAL PROCESSES****Minko O.**

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Abstract

The article analyzes the design of an energy machine. A parametric methodology for modeling and designing electro-mechanical energy converters is developed, which is based on the provisions of parametric design with one search criterion, or solution. The use of modern modeling tools is shown, which allows implementing such methods of system analysis as creating a criterion function with several indicators, using the properties of two or more physical parameters (electrical, mechanical, thermal, etc.). The structure of the elements of the power machine body is built using the multiparametric design method, the architecture of the blocks of the project components is determined, the relationships of the structural elements of the design approach and the sequence of calculations and design stages are substantiated. Using the example of the structural component of the body, the main elements are obtained that can be interpreted into the composition of an electric machine for the needs of the metallurgical industry. Emphasis is placed on the fact that, using parametric modeling and calculation and when creating additional software tools, it is possible to significantly increase the functionality of parametric design of individual elements of a power plant.

Keywords: electromechanical energy converter, parametric model, power plant, multiphysical processes.

1. Introduction

In the energy industry, one of the main components of equipment is turbine power machines and installations. The structural model of the algorithm for parametric design of electromechanical energy converters is a conceptual diagram that describes the logic and relationships between the design stages, taking into account numerous parameters (geometric, electrical, thermal, economic, technological, operational, etc.). Such a model is the basis for building optimized solutions in complex electromechanical systems [1].

The design stage is a complete and independent set of measures for developing a certain amount of design work, which may include calculations, modeling, drawings, experimental research and testing. The formation of the quantity and composition of the project depends on the developer and ranges from 1 to m design stages. We propose to distinguish the following stages of multiparametric design of electrical machines (EM) [2]:

1. Selection of the main dimensions of the electrical machine;
2. Calculation of the stator winding;
3. Calculation of the rotor winding;
4. Determination of the parameters of the electromagnetic circuit;
5. Determination of the operating characteristics of the electric machine;
6. Development of the structural part of the electric machine;
7. Development of the cooling system and its functional units.

The purpose of the article is to formulate the methodology, algorithms, and scientific and technical theory for performing parametric development of a turbine power machine, taking into account the multiphysical processes that arise in it during operation: electrodynamic, gas-dynamic, thermal, and mechanical.

2. Materials and research methods

In the actual theoretical study, we will consider point 6 – the development of the structural part of the electric machine.

Determining the geometry of the inactive (structural) zone of the electromechanical energy converter in parametric design is a design stage that covers the calculation and formation of parts of the EM that do not take a direct part in the electromagnetic conversion of energy, but ensure its mechanical integrity and cooling, meet transportation and installation requirements, ensure operational reliability and provide for the connection to the EM of various communications and support systems (connection to the electrical network, connection to water, hydrogen, lubrication and connection to networks of automatic control and monitoring of the technical condition of the EM) [3].

Figure 1 presents the developed graphical model for determining the geometry of the inactive zone of the electro-mechanical energy converter in parametric design. We have formulated four physical components of the design stage, which aims to determine the indicators of the structural part of the EM [4]:

Fig. 1 – Structural model of the algorithm for determining the geometry of the inactive zone of an electric machine during parametric design

1. Electromagnetic indicators: i_v – excitation current of the thyristor excitation system, or brush holder apparatus, excitation control signals in the range of 4 – 20 mA, additional amount of electrical energy losses from the design features of the inactive EM zone;

2. Electromechanical indicators: G_{Fe} – mass of active steel of the EM stator, G_{Cu} – mass of the EM stator winding, Q_m – electrical energy losses in the EM bearings; reactions of the EM supporting parts (outer legs) to mechanical loads and vibrations during EM operation, development of the EM housing design taking into account excess hydrogen pressure (if provided) under the EM housing, and much more;

3. Heat and ventilation indicators: shape and geometry in the radial partitions of the stator, separation of conditionally hot cooling gas flows from conditionally cold ones, analysis of the hydraulic resistance of

the gas that performs cooling and analysis of local places of temperature excess;

4. Operational indicators: determination of the technology for mounting the EM on the foundation, determination of the technology for inserting the rotor into the stator (for powerful turbogenerators, the development of technological equipment is required), execution of the design in compliance with the requirements for connection to hydrogen, water, lubricant, control circuits, etc. The mathematical model of parametric determination of the EM construction zone (Y_{korp}) is very broad in its multiphysical sense, therefore we limited ourselves to calculating mechanical loads from the EM's own mass, electrical power losses in bearings and EM excitation losses, for the reasons that these indicators are the most influential from the economic side of the design process:

$$Y_{korp}f(G_{FC}; Q_v; Q_m) = \begin{cases} G_{FC} = G_{Fe} + G_{Cu}, \\ Q_v = \frac{2 \cdot i_n + (i_n^2 \cdot r_2)}{\eta_v}, \\ Q_m = 255 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{G_2}{2} \cdot \frac{l_b}{d_b}} \cdot d_b^2 \cdot \left(\frac{f_n}{50 \cdot p}\right). \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where, η_v – efficiency of the excitation device, a.u.; G_2 – mass of the rotor with the winding, kg; l_b – width of the bearing insert that is connected to the rotor, mm; d_b – diameter of the bearing insert that is connected to the rotor, mm; G_{FC} – total mass of the stator core G_{Fe} and the stator winding G_{Cu} , which are determined as follows:

$$G_{Fe} = 5.97 \cdot (D_a^2 - D_{z1}^2) \cdot l_1 + 7.62 \cdot z_1 \cdot h_{n1} \cdot \left(\frac{b'_{z1} + b_{z1}}{2}\right) \cdot l_1; \quad (2)$$

$$G_{Cu} = 1.5 \cdot r_1 \cdot (q_{a1} \cdot a_1)^2, \quad (3)$$

where, D_{z1} – is the stator diameter at the bottom of the stator groove, mm; D_a – outer diameter of the stator core, mm; b'_{z1} and b_{z1} are the width of the stator core tooth at the bottom of the stator slot, and the width of the stator core tooth at the inner diameter of the stator core, mm; h_{n1} – depth of the stator core groove, mm; z_1 – number of stator slots, pcs.; a_1 – number of parallel branches of the stator winding; q_{a1} – number of slots per pole and phase; l_1 – stator core length, mm; r_1 – radius of rounding of the corners of the copper elementary conductor of the rotor winding, mm;

For a better understanding of the geometry of the calculation zone of the power machine, we have depicted a schematic model in which we have shown the main designations, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 – Graphical model of the computational domain in mathematical modeling of an energy machine

3. Results and discussion

Parametric construction of the housing part of the basic electric machine is a multifaceted engineering design process aimed not only at mechanical protection, but also at ensuring heat dissipation, vibration reduction, electrical insulation and compliance with operating standards in specified operating conditions. From the design point of view, the housing part of the EM has the following features [5, 6]:

- accuracy of tolerances (especially important when fitting bearings or interacting with axial structural elements);
- insulating properties (prevention of electric current breakdowns, especially in traction and high-voltage machines);

- electromagnetic shielding (in high-frequency motors, powerful EM or special-purpose EM).

- modularity or nodality (for maintenance: housing sectioning, the presence of hatches, hinged sections, etc.).

The synthesis of the body part of the basic EM using parametric design is graphically shown in Figure 3, and the execution of design work using this process will allow determining the layout of the main structural elements of the EM - the type of stator housing, the type of extension boxes (symmetrical, non-symmetrical, vertical, horizontal), the method of connecting the EM to the foundation, and the connection of the bearing assembly to the EM body.

Fig. 3 – Construction of the body part of the basic electric machine using parametric design

General attributes of EM for the synthesis of the housing part differ from the construction of other nodes of the electromechanical energy converter by the presence of recommendation information on the distance between the bearings (h_b) which is due to the experience of designing EM of various types and is given in more detail in [7, 8], and the presence of variants of the design of EM with several bearings - one (when the function of the second bearing is performed by the adjacent bearing on the shaft line, for example, a turbine), or two.

Regarding the indicators specified by the project and data from the previous stages of design, the following information should be noted, which is necessary for the parametric construction of the EM housing: the indicator of excess gas pressure in the EM housing (H_{em}), the average temperature over the housing (T_{em}), the stator mass (G_s), the rotor mass (G_r), the total rotor length (l_r) and the total stator length (l_s). Without all these indicators, it is impossible to perform further calculations and parametric determinations.

The first parametric block is the definition of the type of flexible connection of the EM with the foundation - for powerful machines there are two types of such connection, this is the so-called double housing, when the stator core is stacked on prisms and transverse diaphragms, which together form a frame (housing) that holds the core with the winding, and this housing itself is installed in the outer housing using flexible elements (springs) that are located four pieces in different planes,

and the number of such springs depends on the length of the stator core and its mass together with the winding. Thus, the limitation of stator vibrations occurs in the middle of the EM and the mechanical load is not transmitted to the external supporting structures of the EM that are connected to the foundation by a rigid connection. The second type of connection contains one external housing in which the stator core is stacked and the connection of the EM housing with the foundation occurs using flexible external supports (spring legs). Both design options are considered in detail in [9, 10]. Also in this block the reaction of the support (m_0) to mechanical loads from the EM is calculated, and the width (h_p), length (l_p), thickness (b_p) and number (n_p) of spring elements in the flexible support system are calculated.

In the next parametric block the design of the end shields is determined. In powerful machines these shields bear little or no mechanical load, especially when it comes to EMs with a capacity of 600 – 1000 MW. By and large, the design of the end shields can be divided into two types: a conventional shield, which consists of the main wall (disk) and radial stiffeners, to increase the resistance to mechanical loads. The second option is when the lower half of the outer shield is connected to the bearing housing, so that part of the shield performs the function of part of the bearing housing, and these two elements together perceive mechanical loads during the operation of the EM. Each design option has its own advantages and disadvantages, and

they are studied in detail in [11, 12]. In the scope of this block, it is necessary to calculate such indicators as: thickness (b_a) and diameter (b_d) of the end shield disk, thickness (b_r) and number (b_n) of radial stiffeners, and wall thickness of the bearing housing (b_b).

In the last multiparametric design block, it is necessary to determine the properties of the material under operating conditions (mainly temperature) – structural steel, and non-magnetic steel. The yield strength of the material (σ_{st}) and the coefficient of linear expansion (ξ_{st}) are mandatory.

In the final block, the mechanical load on the housing and box (σ_k), flexible springs (σ_p) and end shield (σ_{ts}) is calculated. Then the EM layout is selected, the most common are four layout options:

a) double casing, two vertical boxes for heat exchangers. The entire structure is rigidly fixed to the foundation. Such layouts are inherent in turbogenerators with a hydrogen or mixed cooling system, with a capacity of 200 – 500 MW;

b) double casing, one horizontal box for heat exchangers. The entire structure is rigidly fixed to the foundation. Such layouts are used in turbogenerators

with a hydrogen or mixed cooling system, with a capacity of 300 – 350 MW;

c) single casing, two vertical boxes for heat exchangers. The box is rigidly fixed to the foundation, the stator is mounted on flexible supports. Such a design is used in turbogenerators with an air or mixed cooling system, with a capacity of 100 – 200 MW;

d) single casing, one box for heat exchangers, located on top of the stator. The box and stator are connected to the foundation through flexible supports of the stator housing. This arrangement is observed mainly in turbogenerators with an air cooling system, with a capacity of 20 – 120 MW;

As a result of performing all the above-mentioned measures for parametric design, we will obtain a sketch of the general appearance of the EM indicating its main dimensions and the mass of the stator and rotor. The main technical solutions for the arrangement of the main nodes of the EM will also be determined. An example of the structural parts of the EM housing, which can be obtained as a result of parametric synthesis, is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 – Elements of the body part of the electric machine obtained as a result of parametric construction: a – inner core body; b – inner flexible element (spring); c – outer stator body; d – outer end shield.

4. Conclusions

1. Multiparametric methodology for modeling and designing electromechanical energy converters has been developed, which is based on the provisions of parametric design with one search criterion, or solution. The use of modern modeling tools allows implementing such methods of system analysis as creating a criterion function with several indicators, using the properties of two or more physical parameters (electrical, mechanical, thermal, etc.).

2. The weaving of the body elements of the power machine was built using the parametric design method, the architecture of the project's component blocks was

determined, the interrelationships of the structural elements of the design approach and the sequence of calculations and design stages were substantiated. Using the example of the construction of the body component, basic elements were obtained that can be interpreted into the composition of an electric machine for the needs of the metallurgical industry.

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